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DEMOGRAPHIC PERIPHERY OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA: TRENDS AND CHALLENGES IN LOW-POPULATION MUNICIPALITIES*AUTHORS****Alma Kadušić***

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*ABSTRACT****Demographic Periphery of Bosnia and Herzegovina: Trends and Challenges in Low-Population Municipalities***

The current administrative division of Bosnia and Herzegovina was primarily defined by the Dayton Peace Agreement in 1995 and has resulted in a unique political structure of the country. This political division shaped the settlement network, leading to ethnic segregation, territorial fragmentation, and the creation of low-population municipalities. These municipalities are mostly characterized by adverse demographic trends, including emigration, low fertility, and population ageing. This research therefore aims to analyze demographic trends in low-population municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina during the period 2013-2023. However, demographic analysis of low-population municipalities is challenging, since these municipalities represent demographic outliers which skew the analysis and potentially mask the actual demographic trends.

For this reason, data smoothing using Empirical Bayes Rates was applied in order to improve data reliability and identify municipalities that deviate significantly from national average demographic trends. The results of the study are relevant for future demographic research in Bosnia and Herzegovina and may also inform case studies and strategic demographic planning at both the national and regional levels.

KEY WORDS

Demographic trends, periphery, low-population municipalities, demographic outliers, Empirical Bayes rates, Bosnia and Herzegovina

1. Introduction

The administrative division of Bosnia and Herzegovina after the Dayton Peace Agreement resulted in a unique political structure with two entities, Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FBiH) and Republika Srpska (RS), as well as Brčko District of Bosnia and Herzegovina (BDBiH), which has special administrative status (Kapić, 2022; Korkut and Mulalić, 2009). This administrative organization significantly influenced the settlement network, leading to ethnic segregation, territorial fragmentation and division of many municipalities. As a result, low-population municipalities emerged under adverse demographic conditions, leading to significant consequences for the economic and political development of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Avdić et al., 2022; Mirić, 2006).

Low-population municipalities are local administrative units characterized by small number of residents and very often face demographic challenges like population decline (Lešková and Vaishar, 2019). According to González and Soler-Vaya (2024), depopulation of small rural municipalities is a global problem, but it is particularly serious issue in most European countries. As a result, numerous studies have addressed demographic developments in low-population municipalities. For example, Geys et al. (2008) determined that such municipalities in Germany are mostly characterized by lower fertility, growing elderly population and higher dependency ratio. According to Lešková and Vaishar (2019) very small municipalities in Czech Republic often face population ageing and population decline, and they are mostly located in peripheral areas, while Shakhnazarovi (2023) highlighted that low population density is one of the most significant factor of adverse depopulation processes in rural areas of Georgia.

Previous research on the demographic development in Bosnia and Herzegovina indicate unfavourable demographic trends in post-war period such as declining fertility rates, population ageing and intensive emigration (Kadušić et al., 2023; Gekić et al., 2020). According to Avdić and Avdić (2023) depopulation is showing significant regional urban-rural and core-periphery disparities. Adverse demographic trends are mostly followed by low economic and social development. For instance Tandir et al. (2016), as well as Tandir and Konakli (2017) indicate that rural municipalities with similar population density have specific demographic and economic characteristics within the Bosnia and Herzegovina, including migration, unemployment, average net salaries, etc. According to Nezirović (2023) political and socio-economic conditions, including employment and living standards, affect demographic trends in the country. However, although there are numerous studies that treat demographic trends at the level of Bosnia and Herzegovina and its regions, there are few studies that treat the demographic characteristics and trends of the low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Avdić et al., 2022). For this reason, one of the main objectives of this study is the analysis of demographic trends and challenges in low-population municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

In the context of Bosnia and Herzegovina, the concept of demographic periphery refers to municipalities that are both quantitatively and qualitatively marginalized in demographic terms. While the concept of demographic periphery is not explicitly defined in existing literature, it can be incorporated within the broader core-periphery model. Peripheral areas are characterized by weak demographic development, limited socio-economic opportunities and relative spatial isolation from major urban centers (Avdić and Avdić, 2023; Kuolov, 2020). In this study, demographic periphery is pragmatically defined by a quantitative threshold as a municipalities with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants (Figure 1). This criterion captures small local administrative units in Bosnia and Herzegovina that face depopulation, population ageing and low fertility rates, aligning with global and European discussions on rural demographic decline (González and Soler-Vaya, 2024; Lešková and Vaishar, 2019).

However, the demographic periphery in Bosnia and Herzegovina is not only a matter of population size. Many of these municipalities are the product of post-Dayton administrative organization, particularly along the Inter-Entity Boundary Line, where new municipalities were created through territorial fragmentation and ethnic division (Avdić et al, 2022; Raos, 2010; Mirić, 2006).

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2023.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2024).

This restructuring also reinforced the marginal position of municipalities, such as Bosansko Grahovo and Glamoč, which, although not newly established or among the smallest in terms of population, became increasingly peripheralized due to administrative fragmentation, outmigration and the erosion of their functional and economic roles. In this sense, demographic periphery in Bosnia and Herzegovina should be defined as a statistical category of low-population municipalities and as a manifestation of political and spatial restructuring that produced or deepened peripheral demographic trends. Analysis of demographic trends in low-population municipalities is very often challenging since these local administrative units very often represent demographic outliers that can skew data and hide underlying spatial patterns of demographic development. As stated by Swanson et al. (2020) estimating crude rates in small population needs to acknowledge the high stochastic uncertainty which leads to significant annual variations.

This variability can misrepresent true demographic trends and lead to misleading conclusions. Accordingly, additional methods of statistical analysis must be taken into consideration when performing demographic analysis in order to enhance data accuracy and identify municipalities with most adverse population trends in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Therefore, main goal of this study is to analyze demographic trends in low-population municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina in the period from 2013 to 2023 using data on birth and death rates, fertility, ageing coefficient and average age. By applying Empirical Bayes Rates, which are determined as a weighted average between the raw rate for each municipality and the national average, with weights proportional to the underlying population at risk (Yue and Hu, 2021; Anselin, 2005) this study aims to enhance data accuracy, identify demographic outliers or municipalities that significantly deviate from the average demographic trends in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The study will be framed within the theoretical framework of demographic transition theory which explains changes in population dynamics, and spatial demography concept which explores the influence of geographical factors on population spatial distribution and demographic characteristics. These concepts will contribute to understanding of the influence of political division and territorial fragmentation on demographic changes in peripheral areas or municipalities. By addressing these issues in demographic analysis, the study results will offer a basis for conducting future case studies and defining strategies of demographic development at national and regional level. The research results are also significant for future demographic studies providing new insight into demographic spatial disparities and specific trends of low-population municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

2. Methodology

The complex development of the settlement system in Bosnia and Herzegovina resulted in a specific spatial structure of settlements of different hierarchical ranks, and was conditioned by the spatial distribution of the population, economic activities and supporting infrastructure. Dayton Peace Agreement in 1995 and the political-territorial organization of Bosnia and Herzegovina into two entities, and the establishment of the Brčko District by the decision of the Arbitration Commission in 2000, caused a restructuring of the settlement system and the disintegration of a large number of municipalities and settlements compared to the population census in 1991 (Avdić et al., 2022; Mirić, 2006).

According to Avdić et al. (2022), this led to significant changes in the internal regional structure and the concept of regional development, but also changes at the local level, where the number of municipalities since 1991 increased from 109 to 143.

Data analysis plan for the demographic analysis of low-population municipalities included collecting data on general fertility rate, crude birth and death rates, ageing coefficient and average age for the period 2013 to 2023, from publications, bulletins and sources from statistical institutions in Bosnia and Herzegovina, including Agency for Statistics of Bosnia and Herzegovina (BHAS), Institute for Statistics of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (FZS), and Republika Srpska Institute of Statistics (RZSRS). In order to determine general fertility rate and average age in municipalities of Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, raw data on age structure of the population by five-year groups, provided on request by the Institute for Statistics of Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, were used. For the municipalities of the entity of Republika Srpska, population estimates by five-year groups for 1996-2024 from the Republika Srpska Institute of Statistics were used.

When analysing demographic data for low-population areas, especially crude rates, the high stochastic uncertainty which leads to significant yearly variations must be acknowledged (Swanson et al., 2020). This means that population size affects rates which can vary significantly in a large fluctuations from year to year due to chance. According to the 2013 Population Census of Bosnia and Herzegovina, five municipalities had fewer than 1,000 residents, eight had populations between 1,000 and 2,000, and 15 had populations between 2,000 and 5,000. Estimates for 2023 indicate that seven municipalities had fewer than 1,000 residents, nine had populations between 1,000 and 2,000, and 15 had populations between 2,000 and 5,000. All remaining municipalities in both years had populations exceeding 5,000 (Figure 1).

In order to eliminate the effect of population size on demographic statistics and detect demographic outliers, the smoothing of crude rates by Empirical Bayes Rates in GeoDa was performed. This approach will allow the identification of municipalities that significantly deviate from average demographic trends in Bosnia and Herzegovina. In demographic studies, crude rates of population change are typically calculated as the number of births or deaths relative to the total population (Nejašmić, 2005). The estimation accuracy of these crude rates depends on the count of the denominator, and spatial units with small population are likely to have less accurate calculations (Yue and Hu, 2021).

As stated in studies by Yue and Hu (2021) and Swanson et al. (2020), differences in population size very often cause the issue of high stochastic uncertainty or variance instability and outliers in crude rates. As indicated by Anselin (2005), Empirical Bayes (EB) approach is a smoothing technique which smooths the raw data or raw rates towards the overall state average. The basic principle of Empirical Bayes Smoothing is to improve data accuracy by computing a weighted average between the raw rate for every municipality and the national average, with weight proportional to the underlying population at risk (Yue and Hu, 2021; Anselin, 2005).

When calculating EB rates, $r_i = y_i/n_i$ is observed as a rate of geographical unit "i", where y_i represents the count observed, and n_i represents population size. The unknown rate in the geographical unit "i" is denoted as λ_i . Assuming the underlying rates are independent samples from a prior probability distribution, with mean μ_i , and variance φ_i , the Empirical Bayes smoothing of λ_i is a weighted combination of r_i and μ_i (Yue and Hu, 2021):

$$\hat{\lambda}_i = w_i r_i + (1 - w_i) \mu_i$$

r_i is the observed (crude) rate for area "i",

μ_i is the reference rate (e.g. national average),

w_i is the weight assigned to area "i", typically based on its population size, and it depends on φ_i , μ_i , and n_i .

Given the methodological framework previously described, this study represents a quantitative research with the aim to analyze basic demographic indicators in Bosnia and Herzegovina. This approach will allow the measurement and comparison of spatial and temporal changes of demographic trends over the research period 2013 to 2023, and identification of municipalities with the most unfavourable demographic trends, with a focus on low-population municipalities (Figure 2). Research results will be geovisualized in the form of maps, charts, and structured tables, enabling municipal-level comparison between 2013 and 2023. This includes comparisons of crude and smoothed rates in order to highlight the impact of Empirical Bayes Smoothing (EBS) technique.

Figure 2: Research methodology phases.

3. Results and Discussion

Bosnia and Herzegovina faces significant demographic challenges, including decreasing population biodynamics, population ageing and emigration (Gekić et al., 2020; Pobrić and Robinson, 2015). Population decline in this country is caused by natural depopulation and emigration of young and fertile population (Kadušić et al., 2023; Jahić et al., 2024; Efendić, 2016). Natural depopulation is characterized by low total fertility rate, which is below replacement level (Pobrić and Robinson, 2015), with death rates exceeding birth rates (Kadusic et al., 2023), additionally aggravated by population ageing (Gekić et al., 2019). Similar demographic trends are also noticeable in the selected period from 2013 to 2023, in which Bosnia and Herzegovina continues to face decreasing birth rates, and increasing death rates, ageing coefficient and average age. The data presented in Table 1 indicate adverse demographic trends on the national level of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

In the period from 2013 to 2023 birth rate decreased from 8.7‰ to 7.7‰, and fertility rate from 34.7‰ to 33.9‰. In the same period death rate increased from 10.1‰ to 10.4‰, ageing coefficient from 14.4% to 19.2%, and average age from 39.6 to 42.5. Initial geovisualization of crude rates of population biodynamics, ageing coefficient and average age indicated temporal and spatial differences in demographic trends during the researched period (Figure 3, 4 and 5).

Table 1: Demographic trends in Bosnia and Herzegovina in the period 2013 to 2023.

Year	Birth rate (%)	Fertility rate (‰)	Death rate (%)	Ageing coefficient (%)	Average age
2013	8.7	34.7	10.1	14.4	39.6
2014	8.6	34.2	10.2	14.8	39.9
2015	8.5	33.7	10.8	15.3	40.3
2016	8.6	35.7	10.4	15.3	40.6
2017	8.6	35.7	10.8	16.0	40.8
2018	8.4	36.2	10.8	16.6	41.1
2019	8.1	34.8	11.1	17.2	41.4
2020	7.8	34.0	12.8	17.8	41.7
2021	7.9	34.2	14.6	18.1	41.9
2022	7.8	33.9	12.0	18.6	42.2
2023	7.7	33.9	10.4	19.2	42.5

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2013-2025).

Figure 3: General fertility rate by municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2013 and 2023.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2013-2025).

Figure 4: Death rate by municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2013 and 2023.
Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2013-2025).

Figure 5: Ageing coefficient by municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2013 and 2023.
Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2013-2025).

It is evident that, in the period from 2013 to 2023, significant demographic changes occurred, and the decline in potential biodynamics and ageing of the population are visible at the level of entire Bosnia and Herzegovina. Although noticeable, changes in the trend of fertility and death rates are not significantly expressed (Figures 3 and 4). More significant changes are noticeable in the population ageing process (Figure 5), which indicates advanced population ageing at the level of entire Bosnia and Herzegovina. However, adverse demographic trends are not of equal intensity in all regions. The evidence show that certain areas of Bosnia and Herzegovina are facing unfavorable demographic trends. Thus, the areas of central Bosnia and northwestern Bosnia record more favourable demographic trends compared to the rest of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Unfavourable trends are present in sparsely populated rural areas, and the presented data indicate a pronounced urban-rural polarization on this matter.

However, certain irregularities related to high fertility and low death rates in certain municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina that have a very small number of inhabitants are visible in the figures. These crude rates, for municipalities with small populations, are unstable, variable and can potentially be misinterpreted. Tables 2 and 3 show data on basic demographic trends, i.e. trend of general birth rate, fertility rate, death rate, ageing coefficient and average age in municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina with less than 5,000 inhabitants.

From the data presented in Tables 2 and 3, it is noticeable that some low-population municipalities in observed years recorded a fertility rate of 0.0‰, while some municipalities with a small population had the same parameter as high as 79.4‰. For instance, in 2013, the municipality of Istočni Drvar recorded a fertility rate of 0.0‰, and in 2023, a general fertility rate of 66.7‰. Similar variability can be found in death rate, which varied from 0.0‰ to 30.5‰ in low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina in the observed years. For example, the municipality of Domaljevac-Šamac recorded a death rate of 9.9‰ in 2013, and 1.8‰ in 2023.

Table 2: Demographic trends in low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2013.

Municipality	Population	Birth rate (‰)	Fertility rate (‰)	Death rate (‰)	Ageing coefficient (%)	Average age
Istočni Drvar	77	0.0	0.0	12.7	13.0	49.0
Kupres-RS	294	10.0	93.8	20.0	46.3	54.1
Istočni Mostar	255	0.0	0.0	3.9	27.5	46.0
Petrovac	357	13.9	79.4	30.5	26.9	46.0
Pale-FBiH	904	8.8	40.6	5.5	19.8	42.5
Jezero	1041	7.0	35.7	13.1	15.6	41.5
I. Stari Grad	1134	4.4	29.6	23.9	26.7	48.1
Krupa na Uni	1565	4.4	28.6	16.9	26.4	46.3
Dobretići	1638	1.8	7.9	11.0	13.2	42.2
Kalinovik	1971	5.9	39.5	23.2	27.2	48.2
Foča-FBiH	1949	3.6	18.4	9.3	22.7	44.0
Berkovići	2052	9.5	56.3	17.5	25.7	44.3
Trnovo-FBiH	1590	7.3	43.1	17.3	25.7	48.8
Trnovo-RS	1981	2.9	16.0	11.2	21.5	46.1
Oštra Luka	2715	7.9	42.6	20.8	20.6	43.0
B. Grahovo	2449	4.5	34.0	14.3	33.4	52.1
Novo Goražde	2938	2.2	12.0	6.7	17.8	44.6
Ljubinje	3327	6.6	34.9	14.8	20.3	44.0
Han Pijesak	3459	7.9	41.1	11.3	22.4	45.7
Donji Žabar	3650	0.3	1.3	6.8	20.4	42.8
Ravno	3218	0.0	0.0	0.6	20.1	43.4
Glamoč	3887	6.2	33.6	14.5	26.9	45.9
Pelagićevo	4347	0.2	1.3	10.5	26.9	47.6
Doboj-Jug	4148	10.6	41.0	9.9	8.7	35.8
Vukosavlje	4365	8.8	42.9	10.1	15.5	41.2
Čajniče	4685	7.2	38.3	12.3	19.1	43.0
Dom.-Šamac	4774	3.4	13.2	9.9	15.1	40.1
Neum	4671	0.6	2.9	8.6	16.9	41.2

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2013-2025)

Table 3: Demographic trends in low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2023

Municipality	Population	Birth rate (‰)	Fertility rate (‰)	Death rate (‰)	Ageing coefficient (%)	Average age
Istočni Drvar	106	9.4	66.7	0.0	22.6	46.9
Kupres-RS	218	4.6	58.8	18.3	51.3	60.6
Istočni Mostar	241	4.1	26.3	0.0	30.7	51.7
Petrovac	638	7.8	61.7	28.2	31.7	48.7
Pale-FBiH	774	3.9	24.2	19.4	27.5	47.7
Jezero	924	10.8	54.6	11.9	22.9	46.3
I. Stari Grad	954	10.5	74.6	24.1	33.9	48.7
Krupa na Uni	1244	8.0	50.0	24.1	26.1	47.9
Dobretići	1508	2.0	10.5	6.6	20.9	49.2
Kalinovik	1570	6.3	41.3	24.8	32.0	50.3
Foča-FBiH	1697	4.7	26.5	13.6	28.9	47.7
Berkovići	1710	2.9	17.8	18.7	28.9	47.9
Trnovo-FBiH	1774	9.6	51.7	20.9	28.5	45.7
Trnovo-RS	1960	4.5	30.7	11.7	34.7	52.0
Oštra Luka	1977	12.1	67.6	31.3	23.5	44.5
B. Grahovo	1997	1.0	8.4	12.0	41.5	55.9
Novo Goražde	2484	4.4	24.0	6.8	31.3	50.7
Ljubinje	2943	9.5	55.1	19.7	25.3	45.9
Han Pijesak	3050	7.2	42.9	18.7	28.5	48.2
Donji Žabar	3207	1.0	5.2	10.3	29.3	50.3
Ravno	3218	0.0	1.7	0.3	32.5	52.0
Glamoč	3274	4.6	26.6	11.0	31.6	49.0
Pelagićevo	3682	1.9	12.4	17.4	33.5	52.9
Doboj-Jug	4097	8.8	36.5	8.8	13.0	38.6
Vukosavlje	4147	5.0	25.2	10.3	21.2	44.2
Čajniče	4180	7.9	46.4	12.7	26.3	47.0
Dom.-Šamac	4325	7.6	7.7	1.8	19.4	45.7
Neum	4342	4.0	17.1	3.5	25.6	47.8
Kupres-FBiH	4747	4.5	58.8	18.3	51.4	60.6
Kreševo	4778	3.6	16.7	11.3	20.9	44.2
Ribnik	4846	5.2	29.2	22.7	28.1	47.0

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRS, 2013-2025)

The previously presented data indicate that calculating crude birth, fertility and death rates at the level of small-population municipalities often produces distorted results, as these indicators tend to exhibit pronounced year-to-year fluctuations that do not reflect genuine demographic trends. This is why sometimes small populations record a high fertility rate or a low death rate, even

though it is essentially just a statistical aberration due to a small population base. In demographic analysis, such data can cause "noise" and distort the demographic analysis, and must be viewed as demographic outliers. Therefore, it is very important to take this phenomenon into account and use correction methods such as calculating standardized rates, Empirical Bayes smoothing rates, calculating multi-year averages or grouping data to get a more realistic representation of demographic trends. Using the technique of Empirical Bayes smoothing of crude rates of natality, fertility and mortality in Bosnia and Herzegovina for 2013 and 2023 at the municipal level, the accuracy of the data was improved by balancing the weighted average between the crude rates for each municipality and the average rates for Bosnia and Herzegovina, while taking into account the weighting factor that is proportional to the population at risk (Figures 6, 7, 8).

Figure 6: Empirical Bayes smoothed birth rates in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013 and 2023.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRIS, 2013-2025).

Data presented in Figures 6 and 7 are showing that, after applying EBS technique, about 80% municipalities of Bosnia and Herzegovina are in relatively narrow band between the 10th and 90th percentiles (5-10 births per 1000 population, or 21-41 births per 1000 women aged 15-49), i.e. most municipalities do not deviate significantly from the national average of birth and fertility rates. There are 13 municipalities in the 1st to 10th percentile class, and only one municipality is below the 1st percentile with an EB smoothed birth rate below

1‰ and an EB smoothed fertility rate below 12‰. There are 13 municipalities in the 90th to 99th percentile class, and only one municipality exceeds the 99th percentile with a EB smoothed fertility rate greater than 53‰.

Figure 7: Empirical Bayes smoothed general fertility rates in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013 and 2023.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRs, 2013-2025).

Figure 8: Empirical Bayes smoothed death rates in Bosnia and Herzegovina, 2013 and 2023.

Source: Author's calculation (BHAS, FZS, RZSRs, 2013-2025).

With EBS, crude rates in low-population municipalities are pulled towards the national average, while large urban centers kept their weight factor and their smoothed rates changed less in comparison to crude rates.

However, EBS is a technique applied for data smoothing using the demographic trends on national level or neighboring small areas. According to Inoue (2017) Empirical Bayes Smoothing is a representative method used in the analysis of small areas, but it also has limitations.

Table 4: Classification of low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina by general fertility rates (GFR) and EBS fertility rates in 2023.

Class	Municipalities by GFR	Municipalities by EBS
Extremely low	Bosansko Grahovo, Dobretići, Domaljevac-Šamac, Donji Žabar, Pelagićevo, Ravno	
Very low	Berkovići, Kreševo, Neum	Domaljevac-Šamac, Donji Žabar, Ravno, Vukosavlje
Below average	Foča (FBiH), Glamoč, Istočni Mostar, Novo Goražde, Pale, Ribnik, Trnovo (RS), Vukosavlje	Berkovići, Bosansko Grahovo, Čajniče, Dobretići, Foča (FBiH), Glamoč, Kreševo, Neum, Novo Goražde, Pale (FBiH), Pelagićevo, Ribnik, Trnovo-RS
Above average	Doboj Jug, Kalinovik	Doboj Jug, Han Pijesak, Istočni Drvar, Istočni Mostar, Istočni Stari Grad, Jezero, Kalinovik, Kupres (FBiH), Kupres (RS), Krupa na Uni, Petrovac, Trnovo (FBiH)
Very high	Čajniče, Han Pijesak, Krupa na Uni, Trnovo (FBiH)	Ljubinj, Oštra Luka
Exceptionally high	Istočni Drvar, Istočni Stari Grad, Jezero, Kupres (FBiH), Kupres (RS), Ljubinj, Oštra Luka, Petrovac	

That is why the research results presented in Figures 6, 7 and 8, as well as Tables 4 and 5 show certain inconsistencies, even after smoothing of crude rates. Although it is a very useful method for smoothing rates in case of high rates variability in small populations, EBS in extremely spatially heterogeneous areas, such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, it does not provide quality results for all spatial units or municipalities.

Table 5: Classification of low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina by crude death rate (CDR) and EBS death rates in 2023.

Class	Municipalities by CDR	Municipalities by EBS
Extremely low	Domaljevac-Šamac, Istočni Drvar, Istočni Mostar, Neum, Ravno	Ravno
Very low	Dobretići, Novo Goražde	Neum
Below average	Doboj Jug, Donji Žabar, Vukosavlje	Doboj Jug, Dobretići, Domaljevac-Šamac, Donji Žabar, Istočni Drvar, Istočni Mostar, Novo Goražde, Vukosavlje
Above average	Bosansko Grahovo, Čajniče, Foča (FBiH), Glamoč, Jezero, Kreševo, Trnovo (RS)	Bosansko Grahovo, Berkovići, Čajniče, Foča (FBiH), Glamoč, Jezero, Kreševo, Kupres (FBiH), Kupres (RS), Pale (FBiH), Trnovo (RS)
Very high	Berkovići, Han Pijesak, Kupres (FBiH), Kupres (RS), Pelagićevo	Han Pijesak, Istočni Stari Grad, Kalinovik, Krupa na Uni, Ljubinje, Pelagićevo, Petrovac, Ribnik, Trnovo (FBiH)
Exceptionally high	Istočni Stari Grad, Kalinovik, Krupa na Uni, Ljubinje, Oštra Luka, Pale (FBiH), Petrovac, Ribnik, Trnovo (FBiH)	Oštra Luka

After applying the EBS method on the rates of natural biodynamics of the population of Bosnia and Herzegovina for 2013 and 2023, it is noticeable that there are more inconsistencies in the data for birth and fertility rates than death rates. Namely, when calculating fertility rates for small municipalities, the population of women aged 15 to 49 is taken into account as the denominator. In small municipalities, this population can be very small, and only one birth can influence substantial increase in the birth rate. When calculating death rates, the entire population is taken into account, so a larger base is the cause of greater stability of rates. In addition, fertility is a less frequent phenomenon, especially in old and small populations, while mortality occurs in all age groups. Therefore, the size of the population, the frequency of events, the sensitivity of the age structure and the very efficiency of the EBS method influence the greater inconsistencies in the analysis of natality and fertility.

Data presented in Figures 7 and 8, and also in Tables 4 and 5 indicate that EB smoothing of fertility and death rates, taking into account size of population, pulls crude rates toward the national average, which can mask extreme

demographic values and local characteristics of municipalities. Consequently, it is necessary to upgrade research methodology of demographic trends in low-population municipalities, and future research could implement Spatial Empirical Bayes Smoothing, which takes into account the demographic trends of neighboring municipalities, calculate multiple-year average rates and standardized rates which take ageing structure of population into consideration. The lack of official statistics prevent the calculation of standardized rates of fertility and death rates. This indicate that Spatial Empirical Bayes Smoothing could be the next step in the demographic analysis of low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Both applied approaches in the analysis of demographic trends in Bosnia and Herzegovina point to spatial differences in demographic development, where low-population municipalities have the most adverse demographic trends, their trends showing significant year to year variations, and should be, therefore, treated as outliers in demographic analysis. Performed analysis indicate that high ageing coefficient and high death rates correlate, and municipalities in Northwestern and Central Bosnia, urban centres in particular, have more favourable demographic trends in comparison to rural areas in Eastern and Western Bosnia.

There are numerous complex causes of uneven demographic development in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Numerous authors highlight the influence of economic, political and social factors (Kadušić and Zerem, 2025; Avdić and Avdić, 2023; Kadušić et al., 2023). Uneven economic development of Bosnia and Herzegovina includes variations in economic developmental strategies, resource distribution and infrastructure development. These processes affect general unemployment rate, unemployment rate of highly educated population, or net salaries, significantly influencing spatial disparities in demographic development of Bosnia and Herzegovina (Kadušić and Zerem, 2025; Kadušić et al., 2025). This leads to adverse natural population change and net migration, exacerbating disparities among municipalities, and impacting total population dynamics. Mentioned factors shape migration flows and overall population development. As mentioned by Avdić and Avdić (2023) significant societal disparities exists between two entities: Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina and Republika Srpska, but spatial differences in demographic and socio-economic trends are also visible within the entities.

According to Mirić (2006), the disintegration processes caused by the political-territorial division of Bosnia and Herzegovina affected the settlement network and communities of municipalities that were the driver of the country's economic and social development. The political division of Bosnia and Herzegovina affected spatial redistribution of the population and economic activities (Nezirović, 2023), thus deepening demographic challenges, especially in the divided municipalities (Kadušić and Zerem, 2025; Kadušić and Smajić, 2019). According to Pejanović and Osmić (2025) and Marić et al. (2024), the municipalities created along the inter-entity boundary line, on the basis of the Dayton Peace Agreement, represent an example of territorial fragmentation that arose from a political compromise, and not functional territorial organization of the local self-government units of Bosnia and Herzegovina. The establishment of new municipalities was not based on relevant economic, demographic or social criteria, which produced negative consequences for their functionality and sustainability. Delalić et al. (2023) point out that economic and demographic territorial differences between individual regions are the main obstacle to balanced and harmonious development at the regional and national level.

The complex influence of the aforementioned factors contributes to the decline in the demographic biodynamics and vitality of the population in Bosnia and Herzegovina, while these adverse trends are especially pronounced in the low-population municipalities. The analysis of the population development in municipalities with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants indicates a clear decrease in total population in the period from 2013 to 2023, from 69,441 to 62,241, or by 7,200, along with the decline in birth and fertility rates, an increase in death rates, and the growing share of the elderly, which are the clear indicators of the depopulation of small municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Tables 2 and 3). Therefore, a realistic question must be raised about the justified existence of low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, which, in addition to demographic problems, face a lack of human and financial resources, public and market services, investments, jobs, etc. However, similar to some other European countries, for example the Czech Republic or Germany, small local communities have a strong emotional identification and fear of losing public services and autonomy, and very often value independence more than economic and social development (Lešková and Vaishar, 2019). Therefore, similar to the Czech Republic, due to limited political commitment and complex political situation in Bosnia and Herzegovina, municipal consolidation or merger of municipalities is unlikely.

The research results clearly indicate that Bosnia and Herzegovina is experiencing unfavourable demographic trends, and small municipalities of this country are demographically the most vulnerable. For the above reasons, it is necessary to consider the existing concept of local self-government, and propose solutions that would lead to economic, social and demographic sustainability. Therefore, the results of the study are a good basis that can be useful in creating and defining the policy of strategic demographic development of Bosnia and Herzegovina. Although demographic research provides valuable data, there are challenges in its application due to the lack of statistics in Bosnia and Herzegovina and lack of integration of demographic factors into existing development policies. This indicates the need for cooperation between demographers and policy makers in order to ensure the use of the demographic research results in developmental strategies.

4. Conclusion

Research analysis of birth, fertility and death rates, as well as ageing coefficient and average age in Bosnia and Herzegovina, in the period from 2013 to 2023, indicate adverse demographic trends in this country, with low-population municipalities facing the highest levels of depopulation. However, when analyzing the demographic trends of small municipalities, rate variations due to the size of the population are a great issue, and this research especially emphasizes the methodological challenges in demographic research of low-population spatial units. For this reason, the Empirical Bayes Smoothing technique was used in the analysis of demographic characteristics of low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

This technique smooths the crude rates towards the overall national average considering the size of the population. The results of the EBS analysis showed that about 80% of municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina are in relatively narrow band between the 10th and 90th percentiles, and do not deviate significantly from the national average rates. Mainly, low-population municipalities significantly deviate from the national averages, with birth and fertility rates showing greater annual variations. The analysis also pointed to the correlation between death rates and the age coefficient, and significant spatial differences in the level of depopulation in Bosnia and Herzegovina. The areas of central and northwestern Bosnia record more favourable demographic trends compared to the areas of eastern Bosnia and western Herzegovina. The main reasons for demographic changes and unequal demographic development in

Bosnia and Herzegovina are the result of political and territorial changes, but also economic and social factors.

The demographic analysis of municipalities with fewer than 5,000 inhabitants showed a clear decrease in total population in research period by 7,200 inhabitants, which along with the decline in birth and fertility rates, an increase in death rates, and the growing share of the elderly indicates depopulation of small municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina. However, Empirical Bayes Smoothing is a global average rate that pulls extreme values towards the national average, and in extremely spatially heterogeneous areas it does not provide quality results for all municipalities. Therefore, in future research it is necessary to improve the methodology of demographic research of low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and to treat these municipalities as demographic outliers. Future research could apply Spatial Empirical Bayes Smoothing, calculation of multiple-year average rates and standardized rates, which take age structure of population into consideration.

Despite limitations of applied methodology, this study provides useful data for future studies and for policymakers. Considering the economic and demographic issues in low-population municipalities in Bosnia and Herzegovina, local self-government reform and definition of demographic development strategies at the national, regional and local levels are needed. Consequently, there is a necessity of further spatial demographic analysis, and future studies could be used for strategic planning to address country's demographic challenges.

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